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Stability Constants of Rhodizonic Acid Complexes in Solution

SRIKUMAR MUKHERJEE** and NARENDRA S. RAWAT*

Chemical Laboratories, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad-826004

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THE studies of the metal complexes of rhodizonic acid have mostly been done by spectrophotometry¹⁻⁵, and studies by potentiometric method have not received sufficient attention. Therefore the present investigation was undertaken. In the present studies, stability constants of rhodizonic acid with divalent and trivalent metal ions Cu(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), VO(II), UO₂(II), Ca(II), Mg(II), and Al(III) have been calculated by Bjerrum-Calvin's^{6,7} pH titration technique, employing Irving-Rossotti's formula⁸. The thermodynamic stability constants and free energy of formation of these complexes have also been evaluated.

Experimental

Rhodizonic acid (BDH, England), nitrate salt of copper(II), nickel(II), manganese(II), cobalt(II), vanadium(II), cadmium(II), uranyl(II) and aluminium(III) were employed for the studies. In case of magnesium(II) and calcium(II), the carbonates were dissolved in known amounts of nitric acid.

Metallic zinc (BDH, AnalaR) was dissolved in known volume of nitric acid, to obtain zinc(II) nitrate.

The metal contents were estimated by standard methods using EDTA titration⁹ wherever possible. All the metal nitrates were of BDH AnalaR quality.

Perchloric acid (Riedel), sodium perchlorate (Merck) and sodium hydroxide (BDH) were all used for the purpose.

All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water free from CO₂. pH measurements were done by a Philips pH meter using a glass calomel electrode assembly at a constant temperature 27 (± 0.02)° and ionic strength of 0.050M, 0.075M and 0.100M were maintained respectively in each case.

Procedure :

Solution mixture containing (a) acid (5 ml of 0.03M perchloric acid and 5 ml of 0.050M, 0.075M and 0.100M respectively of sodium perchlorate as the case may be), (b) ligand (mixture 'a' and 5 ml of 0.01M RA), (c) complex mixture 'b' and 5 ml of 0.005M metal solution were taken and total volume raised to 50 ml. The mixture (a), (b) and (c) were separately titrated against standard 0.1840M solution hydroxide solution.

Results and Discussion

Values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by Irving-Rossotti's formula. The formation curves corresponding to proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A and \bar{n} against pH and pL respectively.

The formation curves of the ligand extend between 0 and 2 on the \bar{n}_A scale, which supports the dissociation of the ligand in two steps, and this is shown as :

The values of the protonation constants of the ligand are given in Table 1. All calculations were done below the pH at which precipitation occurred.

It was noted that the addition of alkali was accompanied by a gradual change of colour of the ligand and chelate. The colour changes observed in presence of metal ions are almost similar to those observed in their absence. This signifies that metal complexes of similar colour are produced. Initially in an acidic medium, the colour of the ligand is yellowish-red, which gradually changes to red as alkali is added. In the metal-ligand systems also, the colour changed from yellowish-red with increase of pH , the changes being similar with those of the ligand alone.

During the titration of lead-RA system, precipitation occurred from the pH of separation, hence it was not possible to calculate the formation constants. Barium and strontium under the experimental conditions, do not appear to react with RA, as the chelate and ligand curves coincide.

** Dr. S. Mukherjee is now working as a Research Associate in the Department of Chemistry, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad.

TABLE 1—PROTON LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF RHODIZONIC ACID AT TEMPERATURE OF 27°C AND IONIC STRENGTHS OF 0.050M, 0.075M AND 0.100M RESPECTIVELY

Stability Constants	0.05M			0.075M			0.100M			
	log K ₁ H	log β ₂ H	log K ₃	log K ₁ H	log β ₂ H	log K ₃	log K ₁ H	log β ₂ H	log K ₃	
Proton-Ligand Stability Constants	7.40(a) 7.25(b) Mean 7.32	9.56 9.41 Mean 9.48	— — —	7.10(a) 6.95(b) Mean 7.02	9.20 9.05 Mean 9.12	— — —	6.50(a) 6.30(b) Mean 6.40	1.50(c)	8.00 7.80 Mean 7.90	— — —
Metal-Ligand Stability Constants										
Ca(II)-RA	—	9.95(c) 9.80(b) 8.40(b) 13.20	—	—	—	8.48(c) 7.30(b) 3.30(b) 10.60	—	—	—	8.50(c) 3.10(a) 11.60
Ni(II)-RA	—	Mean 9.87 6.85(a) 4.00(a) 10.75	—	—	—	8.07 3.25 11.82	—	—	—	7.40 3.16 10.56
Co(II)-RA	—	6.75(b) 3.95(b) 10.75	—	—	—	6.60(b) 3.88(b) 10.43	—	—	—	6.30(a) 3.60(a) 9.80
Mn(II)-RA	—	Mean 6.80 3.95 19.75	—	—	—	6.67 3.76 10.43	—	—	—	6.11 3.70 9.81
Zn(II)-RA	—	7.10(a) 4.00(a) 11.10	—	—	—	7.00(a) 3.80(a) 10.80	—	—	—	6.40(a) 3.70(a) 10.10
Ca(II)-RA	—	6.80(b) 4.10(b) 10.90	—	—	—	6.85(b) 3.91(b) 10.76	—	—	—	6.18(b) 3.90(c) 10.08
Mg(II)-RA	—	Mean 6.95 4.05 11.00	—	—	—	6.92 3.85 10.77	—	—	—	6.23 3.80 10.09
VO(II)-RA	—	6.40(a) 2.60(c) 9.00	—	—	—	6.30(a) 2.50(c) 8.80	—	—	—	5.70(a) 1.90(c) 7.60
UO ₂ (II)-RA	—	6.23(b) 2.95(b) 9.18	—	—	—	6.13(b) 2.64(b) 8.77	—	—	—	3.53(b) 2.15(b) 7.73
Al(III)-RA	—	Mean 6.81 2.77 9.09	—	—	—	6.21 2.57 8.78	—	—	—	5.64 3.02 7.66
	—	6.90(a) 4.10(a) 11.00	—	—	—	6.55(a) 4.00(a) 10.55	—	—	—	6.10(a) 3.80(a) 9.90
	—	6.76(b) 4.25(b) 11.01	—	—	—	6.30(b) 4.15(b) 10.45	—	—	—	5.95(b) 3.98(b) 9.93
	—	Mean 6.83 4.17 11.00	—	—	—	6.42 4.07 10.49	—	—	—	6.03 3.89 9.91
	—	7.18(a) 2.60(c) 9.78	—	—	—	6.80(a) 2.46(c) 9.26	—	—	—	6.10(a) 2.00(c) 8.10
	—	6.97(b) 2.70(b) 9.67	—	—	—	6.62(b) 6.60(b) 9.22	—	—	—	5.80(b) 2.17(b) 7.97
	—	Mean 7.07 2.65 9.72	—	—	—	6.71 2.53 9.24	—	—	—	5.95 2.08 8.03
	—	6.20(b) — 6.30	—	—	—	6.15(a) — 6.15	—	—	—	5.70(a) — 5.70
	—	6.12(c) — 6.12	—	—	—	6.08(b) — 6.08	—	—	—	5.50(b) — 5.50
	—	Mean 6.16 6.16	—	—	—	6.09 — 6.09	—	—	—	5.06 — 5.06
	—	0.08(a) — 6.08	—	—	—	6.00(a) 3.00(c) 9.00	—	—	—	5.55(a) — 5.55
	—	5.85(b) — 5.85	—	—	—	5.87(b) 2.92(b) 8.79	—	—	—	5.30(b) — 5.30
	—	Mean 5.97 5.97	—	—	—	5.98 2.96 8.89	—	—	—	5.42 — 5.42
	—	6.70(a) 3.70(a) 10.40	—	—	—	6.50(a) 3.50(c) 10.00	—	—	—	6.05(a) 1.95(c) 8.00
	—	6.49(b) 3.90(b) 10.93	—	—	—	6.23(b) 3.81(b) 10.03	—	—	—	5.90(b) 2.90(b) 8.10
	—	Mean 6.59 3.80 10.39	—	—	—	6.36 3.65 10.01	—	—	—	5.97 2.07 8.04
	—	8.30(c) 4.90(a) 13.20	—	—	—	8.15(c) 4.75(a) 12.90	—	—	—	7.30(c) 4.10(a) 11.40
	—	7.42(b) 5.00(b) 12.42	—	—	—	7.10(b) 4.90(b) 12.00	—	—	—	5.92(b) 4.30(b) 10.22
	—	Mean 7.86 4.95 13.81	—	—	—	7.62 4.82 12.44	—	—	—	6.61 4.20 10.81
	—	7.58(c) 4.27(a) 11.80	—	—	—	7.50(c) 4.10(a) 11.60	—	—	—	6.80(c) 3.90(a) 10.20
	—	6.87(b) 4.43(b) 11.40	—	—	—	6.95(b) 4.32(b) 11.37	—	—	—	5.80(b) 4.15(b) 9.95
	—	Mean 7.25 4.35 11.60	—	—	—	7.22 4.21 11.43	—	—	—	6.05 4.02 10.07

(a) interpolation at half \bar{n} value method. (b) interpolation at various \bar{n} value method. (c) mid-point method.

The metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by different methods¹⁰, and the values are given in Table 1.

In cases of Ca(II) and Mg(II), the value of \bar{n} extend up to 1, thus indicating the formation of 1 : 1 complexes in solution. In cases of all the other metal ions studied, the value of \bar{n} extends above 1, but remains below 2, thus confirming the presence of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complex species in solution.

The formation constant K_1 in cases of Mn(II), Ca(II), Mg(II), Vo(II) and Cd(II), were read off directly from the curves by interpolation at half \bar{n} value method or calculated by the method of various \bar{n} values, while the formation constant K_2 corresponding to the second species was evaluated using mid-point method.

The formation curve of Al(III), UO₂(II) and Cu(II) system starts at the value, above $\bar{n}=0.5$, and therefore the $\log K_1$ values for the systems were obtained as difference

$$\log K_1 = \log B_2 - \log K_2.$$

The formation curves of the various systems at an ionic strength of 0.050M are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

FORMATION CURVES, METAL-RA SYSTEM
($\mu = 0.050 M$)

Fig. 1

FORMATION CURVES, METAL-RA SYSTEM
($\mu = 0.050 M$)

Fig. 2

The thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by plotting a graph of $\log K$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ (Figs. 3 and 4.) Extrapolation to zero ionic strength

THERMODYNAMIC FORMATION CURVES OF METAL-RA SYSTEMS

(A) Thermodynamic formation curve
(B) Thermodynamic formation curve

Fig. 3

gave the value of $\log K^{\mu=0}$. Ligational standard free energy was obtained from

$$\Delta F^0 = -RT \ln_2 K^{\mu=0}$$

Fig. 4

The thermodynamic formation constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF RA CHELATES (27°C)

Cation	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂
Cu(II)	15.60	3.95	19.55
Ni(II)	8.45	4.85	13.30
Co(II)	7.40	4.45	11.85
Mn(II)	8.20	3.40	11.60
Zn(II)	8.80	5.00	13.80
Cd(II)	9.60	4.60	14.20
Ca(II)	7.40	—	—
Mg(II)	7.60	—	—
VO(II)	8.00	7.20	15.20
UO ₂ (II)	10.40	7.20	17.60
Al(III)	10.00	5.25	15.25

From the values of formation constants, the relative tendencies of the metal ions studied for complex formation with RA are observed as follows:

From the sequence, it is observed that Irving-William's¹¹ natural order is followed in so far as $\text{Zn} < \text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mn}$ is concerned. It is seen that the stability of Co(II) is greater than Ni(II). This may

be due to the Jahn-Teller stabilisation of Co(II). This anomaly has also been observed by a number of workers¹²⁻¹⁵.

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Potentiometric Study of Some Schiff-Base Ligands

C. R. BERA, S. CHATTOPADHYAY and G. P. SENGUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan, 731235, W. B., India

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SCHIFF bases derived from the reaction of aromatic aldehydes with aliphatic or aromatic amines represent an important series of widely studied ligands¹⁻⁴. The present study reports the proton ligand stability constants for a series of five Schiff-base ligands obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with the amines such as 2-aminopyridine, aniline, anthranilic acid, *o*-aminophenol, and *m*-aminophenol.